

HB and WAB450-24-3-1-P37-HB—were so tolerant that inoculated plants produced statistically higher yields per plant than the control (Tables 1, 2). In FARO 48 and WAB450-I-B-P-33-HB, there was no significant difference between the yield of inoculated and nematode-free plants. These five varieties are considered to be truly tolerant of *M. incognita* and are therefore recommended for further farmer participatory evaluation in West Africa.

This study emphasizes the need to screen all new hybrid lines intended for release to farmers. However, for the older method of screening, one concern is the use of GI as a measure of plant damage. This does not always accurately predict the effect of *Meloidogyne* spp. on yield, the

ultimate test of resistance as far as farmers are concerned. To avoid confusion resulting from such discrepancies, yield must reflect the extent of crop damage and, on this basis, judgment and rating of resistance, tolerance, susceptibility, or hypersusceptibility can be made. GI can be regarded as a preliminary measure of plant reaction to infection by the nematode.

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Evaluation of CMS lines for various floral traits that influence outcrossing in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.)

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Outcrossing was reported to be a function of floral morphology and flowering behavior of both the A lines and the male parents (Oka and Morishima 1967). This study was carried out to evaluate the extent of variation in floral traits in some common A lines.

The experimental materials were composed of 15 male sterile (A) lines and their maintainers (B). The traits evaluated were days to 50% flowering, panicle emergence, and average period of time (in minutes) from the opening of lemma and palea of individual florets to closing of the florets. The angle of lemma and

palea at peak anthesis (in degrees) was measured when the floret was fully opened. The size of the stigma (mm²) was likewise calculated. Broad-sense heritability was calculated using the method of Hanson et al (1956).

The floral traits of 15 cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines and their maintainers were evaluated under different environments (Table 1). In general, the A lines showed longer duration of opening of lemma and palea, poorer panicle exertion, more pronounced stigma traits, and wider angle than the B lines. But IR68888B and CRMS 31B showed

a longer period of floret opening than the A lines. CRMS32B and DRR2B showed a wider angle than their A lines. Although Pusa 5A showed 68.22% panicle emergence and PMS11A showed a small stigmatic surface (0.96 mm²), their other desirable attributes, along with a good opening of lemma and palea, led to a good seed setting (Table 1). Very high coefficients of heritability were found for stigma size, average period of lemma and palea opening, and angle of lemma and palea at peak anthesis (Table 2). The greater the angles of lemma and palea, the greater the exser-

Table 1. Analysis of variance, genetic parameters of variation, and mean performance of 15 cytoplasmic male sterile lines (A) and their maintainer lines (B).^a

Source	df	DAS		PE (%)		DOLP (min)		AOLP (°)		PV(%)		SOS (mm ²)		SS (%)	
		A/B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A
<i>Analysis of variance</i>															
Replication	2	11.07	0.20	2.96	3.25	0.56	1.74	1.33	1.68*	–	0.09	0.003	0.004	0.01	0.15
Treatment	14	246.11**	266.77**	40.44**	77.54**	170.00**	151.10**	13.96**	13.17**	–	5.50	0.49	0.43**	26.35**	29.39**
Error	28	7.14	5.81	4.82	1.56	3.62	2.48	0.51	0.32	–	0.04	0.00	–	1.00	0.27
CD at 5%		4.47	4.03	3.67	2.13	3.06	2.63	1.20	0.95	–	0.35	0.09	0.14	1.70	0.87
<i>Genetic parameters of variation</i>															
Mean		92.75	89.70	71.70	90.90	52.32	50.39	23.96	22.82	–	96.26	1.16	0.96	23.22	81.54
CV (%)		2.88	2.68	3.06	2.61	3.50	3.12	2.99	2.49	–	0.22	4.74	3.06	4.29	0.63
Range (max)		105.66	102.66	80.04	98.00	67.50	60.33	27.73	26.60	0.00	98.50	2.24	2.11	28.29	87.55
Range (min)		78.33	74.33	66.49	83.83	40.50	39.16	21.00	19.73	0.00	93.66	0.60	0.57	16.95	76.54
Variance (P)		86.79	92.79	16.69	26.88	59.08	52.01	4.99	4.60	–	1.86	0.15	0.20	9.45	9.97
Variance (G)		79.65	86.98	11.87	25.32	55.46	49.53	4.48	4.28	–	1.82	0.16	0.21	8.45	9.70
PCV		10.04	10.74	5.70	5.99	14.67	14.31	9.33	9.40	–	1.42	35.21	39.49	13.24	3.87
GCV		9.62	10.40	4.81	5.38	14.24	13.97	8.83	9.07	–	1.40	34.89	39.38	12.51	3.82
<i>Mean performance</i>															
COMS8A/B		78.83	74.33	74.80	97.16	40.50	39.16	21.40	20.20	0.00	97.16	1.21	0.90	20.82	84.53
COMS9A/B		82.33	79.33	73.56	87.50	47.50	45.00	24.26	23.73	0.00	94.66	0.89	0.77	23.02	78.37
COMS10A/B		90.00	86.00	68.59	96.88	47.16	39.50	24.00	21.06	0.00	95.83	1.20	1.05	22.00	84.16
CRMS31A/B		105.66	102.66	72.46	88.82	48.50	51.00	23.66	19.73	0.00	95.16	0.63	0.57	22.90	78.51
CRMS32A/B		100.33	98.00	72.04	92.16	50.66	49.33	21.20	23.40	0.00	97.00	0.79	0.62	21.73	83.62
DRR2A/B		87.66	85.33	70.54	88.83	47.50	44.33	21.00	22.53	0.00	95.03	0.60	0.58	21.51	80.09
Pusa 5A/B		99.00	96.00	68.22	86.61	57.83	56.16	27.13	25.33	0.00	96.16	1.32	1.14	26.01	81.11
IR68886 A/B		78.33	74.66	66.49	86.17	45.50	51.00	24.66	22.73	0.00	96.33	1.24	1.04	20.81	80.50
IR68888 A/B		88.00	84.33	67.29	91.75	45.50	47.66	22.60	21.53	0.00	94.50	1.00	0.68	16.95	79.51
IR68897 A/B		92.00	88.66	71.23	85.29	50.50	45.33	22.40	20.00	0.00	93.66	1.30	1.10	22.12	76.54
IR58025 A/B		89.66	87.33	76.93	97.11	60.66	55.50	27.73	26.60	0.00	98.00	1.59	1.11	26.90	86.50
IR62829 A/B		92.66	89.00	80.04	96.83	67.50	60.83	27.00	25.13	0.00	97.33	2.24	2.11	28.29	87.55
PMS10 A/B		103.00	100.00	69.81	98.00	60.50	60.33	25.73	24.13	0.00	96.33	1.33	0.93	26.54	80.99
PMS11 A/B		104.66	102.33	70.28	87.75	54.66	50.83	23.20	21.86	0.00	98.50	0.96	0.71	25.51	81.68
PMS14 A/B		99.66	97.66	73.30	87.55	60.33	60.00	23.46	24.40	0.00	97.33	1.20	1.15	23.23	79.47

^a = significant at 10% level, * = significant at 5% level, DAS = days to 50% flowering, PE = panicle emergence, DOLP = duration of opening of lemma and palea, AOLP = angle of opened lemma and palea, PV = pollen viability, SOS = size of stigma, SS = seed setting, GCV = genotypic coefficient of variation, PCV = phenotypic coefficient of variation.

Table 2. Broad-sense heritability values (h²) for different floral characters in rice (A lines).

Character	h ² (%)
Days to 50% flowering	91.8
Panicle emergence (%)	71.1
Average period of opening of lemma and palea (min)	94.3
Angle of lemma and palea at peak anthesis (°)	89.7
Size of stigma (mm ²)	98.2
Seed setting (%)	89.4

tion and surface of the stigma, and this led to higher seed setting percentage. These results indicate that visual selection can be used efficiently to identify these traits. High heritability for stigma characteristics was reported by Yang et al (1986) and Neves et al (1989).

The lowest heritability, coupled with the lowest genetic advance, was reported for panicle emergence percentage. In the maintainer lines, high heritability was shown by all traits. With respect to pollen viability percentage, high heritability coupled with the lowest genetic advance was noted. Similarly, Table 3 shows significant phenotypic and environmental correlation coefficients between floral traits and seed setting percentage. In our study, correlations between six characters were worked out in all possible combinations at the phenotypic and genotypic levels for the CMS lines. The magnitude of genotypic correlation coefficients was

greater than the corresponding phenotypic correlation values. This suggests a strong genetic association between the traits and phenotypic expression caused by environmental influence.

Days to 50% flowering and panicle emergence did not show any significant correlation with any of the floral traits at the phenotypic level. Neves et al (1989) reported no correlations between stigma characters. At the environmental level, the average period of lemma and palea opening showed a high and positively significant correlation with panicle emergence percentage.

It can be concluded that floral traits such as duration and

Table 3. Estimates of phenotypic (p), genotypic (g), and environmental (e) correlation coefficient pairs between characters in A lines of rice.^a

Character		Panicle emergence (%)	Average period of lemma and palea opening (min)	Angle of lemma and palea at peak anthesis (A°)	Size of stigma (mm ²)	Seed setting (%)
Days to 50% flowering	g	0.001	0.541	0.131	-0.119	0.495
	p	-0.027	0.503	0.119	-0.115	0.472
	e	-0.0178	-0.008	-0.003	-0.047	0.248
Panicle emergence	g		-0.048	-0.267	-0.540	0.585
	p		0.004	0.243	0.547	0.452
	e		0.528*	0.170	0.089	-0.085
Average period of opening of lemma and palea (min)	g			0.725	0.671	0.854
	p			0.655**	0.641**	0.786**
	e			-0.146	-0.153	0.019
Angle of lemma and palea at peak anthesis (A°)	g				0.707	0.757
	p				0.673**	0.680**
	e			0.229	0.014	
Size of stigma (mm ²)	g					0.555
	p				0.516*	
	e				-0.088	

* = significant at 5% level, ** = significant at 1% level.

angle of opening of florets, size of stigma, and panicle emergence percentage are mainly responsible for influencing outcrossing. Among the A lines, IR62829A, IR58025A, Pusa 5A, PMS10A, and PMS11A showed good rates of

seed setting. These may be recommended for use in hybrid seed production for the upland irrigated ecosystem. On the other hand, IR68888A, IR68888B, and DRR2A exhibited poor performance. New CMS lines should

therefore have a longer floret opening period, bigger stigma surface, and wider lemma and palea angle to increase their seed-setting percentage and to achieve higher yield. Breeders working in hybrid seed production programs should give greater importance to these traits.

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Distribution of *p-SINE1-r2* at the *Wx* locus in cultivated and wild rice in Thailand

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Short interspersed elements (SINEs) are retrotransposons that make their copies by the retroposition of RNA made by RNA polymerase III (Motohashi et al 1997). These are generally found in animals and plants. Umeda et al (1991) and Mochizuki et al (1993) reported the existence of the *p-SINE1* family in rice. Furthermore, Hirano et al (1994) reported that the *p-SINE-r2*, a member of the SINE family, is found only in two

closely related species with the AA genome, *Oryza sativa* and *O. rufipogon*. This element is located in the 10th intron of the *Waxy* gene (Umeda et al 1991). Mochizuki et al (1993) suggested that *p-SINE1-r2* could be useful for classifying various rice strains with the AA genome.

Yamanaka et al (2003) recently suggested that the wild ancestors of *O. sativa* were differentiated into two groups at the *waxy* locus and that this strongly

corresponded to the annual-perennial differentiation in the primary gene pool of *O. sativa*. To shed light on the gene pool of cultivated and wild rice with the AA genome in Thailand, 167 strains consisting of both cultivated species and their wild relatives (*O. nivara* and *O. rufipogon*) were surveyed in terms of *p-SINE1-r2* distribution. Total DNA was isolated from fresh leaves by using the CTAB method (Doyle and Doyle 1987). Polymerase